

Effect of Poisons on the Velocities of Dehydrogenation of (1) Methyl alcohol and (2) Formaldehyde at a Surface of Copper Catalyst Activated with Ceria as Promoter.

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In a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 415) the authors have shown that methyl alcohol can be dehydrogenated on the surface of copper catalyst prepared from copper acetate with thoria or ceria as promoters. These catalysts showed no diminution in activity when worked continuously for about 60 hours. The present investigation was carried out with the object of discovering how various poisonous substances mixed with methyl alcohol would affect the velocity of the following reactions on these catalytic surfaces.

In our previous experiments, the space velocity was very large and methyl alcohol vapour could come in contact with the active catalyst surface for a very short time so that though reaction (1) was almost complete, reaction (2) was almost completely suppressed.

In our present investigation, the experimental arrangement has been so modified that the velocities of reaction (1) and (2) could be separately determined and the influence of poisons on each of these can be studied quantitatively.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The experimental arrangement will be clear from Fig. 1. The reaction tube A was filled with 10 gm. cupric oxide with ceria as promoter and placed inside a vertical electric furnace B. The catalyst was reduced *in situ* by passing a current of pure hydrogen through the open ends C and D for 48 hours at about 180°. After the reduction is complete, the end D is sealed off and the catalyst allowed to cool down in an atmosphere of hydrogen. The reaction tube A is connected to a glass capillary manometer at the top. To prevent condensation of undecomposed methyl alcohol, electric heating coils were placed round the lower limb of the reaction tube

A and also round the capillary tube of the mercury manometer as shown in the diagram. A very small portion E of the capillary at the top was not covered with the heating coil so that the pressure required to bring the mercury meniscus to a certain level in this zone can be easily observed. Methyl alcohol, kept inside a

Fig. 1.

Hoffman's bottle, was dropped into the reaction vessel by opening the cork at C, which was closed immediately after. The temperature of the furnace was kept constant by regulating the electric current, and was noted by means of a long-stem thermometer whose bulb was at the centre of the furnace, close to the catalyst material.

EXPERIMENT No. 1.

No catalyst inside the reaction tube. Glass wool (Merck's guaranteed reagent) washed with pure water was substituted for catalyst.

TABLE I.

0.0346 Gm. of methyl alcohol was introduced.

Temp.	Time after dropping MeOH.	Excess pressure inside the reaction tube.
195°	1 min.	22·3 cm. (of Hg.)
	2 mins.	22·7
	3 mins.	22·7
	15 mins.	22·7

The experiment shows that within a minute after dropping methyl alcohol, the whole of the liquid is converted into vapour, and that the pressure remained steady after the evaporation is completed indicating that methyl alcohol vapour does not undergo any condensation inside the apparatus.

In later experiments with catalysts, it was assumed that methyl alcohol takes about a minute and a half for complete evaporation and the pressure P recorded at that time was taken to be the pressure of undecomposed methyl alcohol vapour. If both the reactions,

are monomolecular on the catalyst surface, then the velocity constants K_1 and K_2 can be easily calculated from the pressure recorded in the manometer. It is clear from the previous paper, that the second reaction takes place only after the first reaction has been almost completed. Obviously when the observed pressure is less than $2P$, we are dealing with the first decomposition ; and

$$P'_{t_1} \text{ (observed pressure at any time } t_1) \\ = P(1-x'_{t_1}) + 2xt_1P \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

$$P'_{t_2} = P(1-x'_{t_2}) + 2x't_2P. \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

where x'_{t_1} is the fraction of methyl alcohol decomposed at time t_1 .

The velocity constant K_1

$$= \frac{1}{t_2-t_1} \log_e \frac{(1-x'_{t_1})}{(1-x'_{t_2})} \\ = \frac{1}{t_2-t_1} \log_e \frac{2P-P_{t_1}}{2P-P_{t_2}} \quad (5)$$

Again when the observed pressure is greater than $2P$ but less than $3P$, reaction (2) is taking place, and

$$P''_{t'} = P + P(1 - x''_{t'}) + 2x''_{t'} P \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

$$P''_{t''} = P + P(1 - x''_{t''}) + 2x''_{t''} P.$$

Where $x''_{t'}$ is the fraction of formaldehyde decomposed at time t' .

The velocity constant K_2

$$= \frac{1}{t'' - t'} \log_e \frac{1 - x''_{t'}}{1 - x''_{t''}} = \frac{1}{t'' - t'} \log_e \frac{3P - P''_{t'}}{3P - P''_{t''}} \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

CATALYST No. 1.

Ten gm. of copper oxide with 0.1% ceria were prepared and reduced according to the method described in the previous paper. The temperature of the furnace was kept at 195° . The pressure due to the evaporation of pure methyl alcohol within $1\frac{1}{2}$ min. after its introduction into the apparatus was 22.8 cm.

TABLE II.

	$T = 195^\circ.$						
	$P = 22.8 \text{ cm.}$						
Time in mins.	t_1	$t_1 + 10$	$t_1 + 15$	$t_1 + 20$	$t_1 + 25$	$t_1 + 30$	$t_1 + 35$
Observed press.	27	31.2	33.1	34.8	36.1	37.3	38.6 cm.
K_1	—	0.0255	0.0264	0.0271	0.0266	0.0269	0.0278

For observed pressure greater than $2 \times 22.8 \text{ cm.}$

Time in mins.	t'	$t' + 6$	$t' + 11$	$t' + 16$	$t' + 21$	$t' + 26$	$t' + 31$	$t' + 36$
Observed press.	46.9	47.6	48.2	48.7	49.3	49.9	50.6	51.3 cm.
K_1	—	0.00552	0.00552	0.00562	0.00575	0.00575	0.00621	0.00621

It will be seen that the monomolecular velocity constants agree very well among themselves and that the velocity constant of dehydrogenation of methyl alcohol is about five times that of decomposition of formaldehyde.

Effect of Poison on Catalyst No. 1.

Poison—Carbon disulphide. Carbon disulphide was mixed with methyl alcohol, and this liquid mixture introduced into the apparatus.

TABLE III.

Weight of catalyst = 8 gm. as copper.

Weight of CS₂ absorbed by the catalyst = 0.00290 gm. $P = 27.3$ cm.

Time in mins.	t_1	$t_1 + 5$	$t_1 + 10$	$t_1 + 15$	$t_1 + 25$
Observed press.	30.6	34.3	36.8	39.2	43.5 cm.
K_1	—	0.0335	0.0299	0.0299	0.0312

For observed pressure greater than 2×27.3 cm.

Time in mins.	t'	$t' + 95$	$t' + 135$	$t' + 155$
Observed press.	63.3	67.5	68.1	69.1 cm.
K_2	—	0.00276	0.00289	0.00239

For very small addition of carbon disulphide, the velocity constant of dehydrogenation of methyl alcohol slightly increases whereas the velocity of decomposition of formaldehyde is almost halved.

TABLE IV.

Wt. of catalyst = 8 gm. as Cu.

Wt. of CS₂ absorbed by catalyst = 0.0230 gm. $P = 18$ cm.

Time in mins.	t_1	$t_1 + 16$	$t_1 + 25$	$t_1 + 45$	$t_1 + 55$
Observed press.	18.5	20.9	21.8	24.3	25.4 cm.
K_1	—	0.0092	0.00828	0.00897	0.0092
K_2	The value of K_2 is negligibly small.				

Complete poisoning is effected when 0.0329 gm. of carbon disulphide is added to this copper catalyst obtained by reduction of 10 gm. of CuO (8 gm. as Cu).

A series of similar experiments were carried out with double the amount of copper catalyst and it was found that for complete poisoning 0.0695 gm. of carbon disulphide was necessary. The diminution in velocity constant, as carbon disulphide was continually increased, was very similar to that observed in the previous case.

Poison—Carbon tetrachloride. Catalyst No. 2 was prepared as before. It should be noted, however, that the activity of a catalyst cannot exactly be reproduced, even though the method

of preparation is the same. It was necessary therefore to measure the velocity constants K_1 and K_2 for pure methyl alcohol for each fresh sample of catalyst.

TABLE V.

Temp. = 195°.

The values of K_1 and K_2 for pure methyl alcohol on the surface of catalyst No. 2 are 0.0253 and 0.00529 respectively and are slightly less than those for catalyst No. 1.

Wt. of catalyst = 8 gm. as Cu.

Wt. of poison (CCl_4) = 0.01212 gm. $P = 19.4$ cm.

Time in mins.	t_1	$t_1 + 1$	$t_1 + 11$	$t_1 + 26$	$t_1 + 41$	$t_1 + 71$	$t_1 + 96$
Observed press	22.1	22.6	26.1	28.0	29.0	30.2	30.7 cm.
K_1	—	0.0299	0.0253	0.0184	0.0138	0.0092	0.00759

It is obvious that K_1 does not remain constant as in the case of carbon disulphide poisoning, but with time the poisoning effect becomes greater and greater and the velocity constant continually diminishes until it reaches a value about $\frac{1}{4}$ of the original value.

Complete poisoning is observed when 0.0241 gm. of carbon tetrachloride is added to 8 gm. of the copper catalyst.

TABLE VI.

Poison—Chloroform.

Catalyst No. 2. Temp. = 195°.

Wt. of poison (chloroform) = 0.01117 gm.

Wt. of catalyst = 8 gm. as Cu.

 P (pressure of undecomposed methyl alcohol vapour) = 22.7 cm.

Time in mins.	t_1	$t_1 + 5$	$t_1 + 13$	$t_1 + 23$	$t_1 + 33$
Observed press.	24.8	29.8	35.2	39.8	43.0 cm.
K_1	—	0.0552	0.0552	0.0552	0.0622

TABLE IV—continued.

For observed pressure greater than 2P.

Time in mins.	t'	$t' + 45$	$t' + 60$
Observed press.	48.1	50.7	51.0 cm.
K_2	—	0.00822	0.00253

With the addition of a small amount of chloroform, the velocity constant of dehydrogenation of methyl alcohol increased to about twice its original value, but the velocity constant of decomposition of formaldehyde showed a considerable falling off from the very beginning. The poisonous action of chloroform is different from that of carbon tetrachloride in that there is no progressive change in the values of the velocity constants with time.

TABLE VII.

Wt. of poison (CHCl_3) = 0.02209 gm.

Wt. of catalyst = 8 gm. as Cu.

Temp. = 195°. $P = 19.8$ cm.

Time in mins.	t_1	$t_1 + 5$	$t_1 + 25$	$t_1 + 40$	$t_1 + 55$
Observed press.	20.0	20.5	22.4	23.3	24.0 cm.
K_1	—	0.00529	0.00529	0.00460	0.00460

Poisoning was complete when 0.03263 gm. of chloroform was added to 8 gm. of the copper catalyst.

Poison—Acetonitrile. Catalyst No. 3 was prepared in a similar way as catalyst No. 1 or No. 2, but when tested with pure methyl alcohol, K_1 and K_2 at 195° were found to be 0.0598 and 0.00759 respectively.

TABLE VIII.

Wt. of poison (acetonitrile) = 0.00728 gm.

Wt. of catalyst = 8 gm. as Cu.

Temp. = 195°. $P = 27.7$ cm.

Time in mins.	t_1	$t_1 + 5$	$t_1 + 15$	$t_1 + 25$	$t_1 + 40$	$t_1 + 60$	$t_1 +$
Observed press.	31.5	33.7	35.5	36.6	37.6	38.2	39.0
K_1	—	0.0184	0.0115	0.0092	0.0089	0.0046	0.00.

As in the case of carbon tetrachloride the velocity constants continually diminishes indicating that it takes some time before the maximum effect of the poison is observed. Acetonitrile appears to be a very violent poison, the velocity constant decreasing about 15 times by the addition 0.00728 gm. of acetonitrile to 8 gm. of copper catalyst. Complete poisoning is effected with 0.0143 gm. of the poison.

Poison—Bromine. Catalyst No. 3 with K_1 and K_2 for pure methyl alcohol 0.0598 and 0.00759 respectively.

TABLE IX.

Wt. of poison (bromine) = 0.01878 gm.

Wt. of catalyst = 8 gm. as Cu.

Temp. = 195°. $P = 22.6$ cm.

Time in mins.	Observed press.	K_1	K_1^2
t_1	26.5 cm.	—	—
$t_1 + 20$	36.0	0.0846	—
$t_1 + 35$	39.2	0.0322	—

For observed pressure greater than $2P$.

t'	46.1 cm.	—	—
$t' + 5$	46.3	—	0.00376

TABLE X.

Wt. of poison (bromine) = 0.1015 gm.

Temp. = 195°. $P = 33.1$ cm.

Time in mins.	Observed press.	K_1
t_1	36.6 cm.	—
$t_1 + 10$	41.9	0.01978
$t_1 + 25$	46.8	0.0213
$t_1 + 40$	50.7	0.0181

With the addition of bromine, the velocity constants K_1 and K_2 both diminish from the very beginning. The full effect for a given amount of poison is perceived immediately, as the velocity constants, in each experiment, are found to agree fairly well with one another.

Dehydrogenation of methyl alcohol stops completely when 0.1677 gm. of bromine is added to 8 gm. of the copper catalyst.

Effect of Iodine.—A large number of experiments were tried with increasing quantities, but no poisoning effect could be detected. In fact, the velocity constants K_1 and K_2 increase as will be clear from Table XI.

TABLE XI.

Wt. of iodine = 1.4715 gm.

Wt. of catalyst No. 3 = 8 gm. as Cu.

Temp. = 195°. $P = 27.7$ cm.

Time in mins.	Observed press.	K_1	K_2
t_1	34.9 cm.	—	—
$t_1 + 2$	38.5	0.0966	—
$t_1 + 7$	44.8	0.0943	—
For observed pressure greater than $2P$.			
t'	61 cm.	—	—
$t' + 5$	62.3	—	0.01196
$t' + 10$	68.5	—	0.01196

TABLE XII.

Poison—Mercuric iodide.

Wt. of $HgI_2 = 0.00176$ gm.

Wt. of catalyst No. 3 = 8 gm. as Cu.

Temp. = 195°. $P = 39.3$ cm.

Time in mins.	Observed press.	K_1	K_2
t_1	43.5 cm.	—	—
$t_1 + 7$	54.9	0.0598	—
$t_1 + 27$	72.5	0.0644	—
For observed pressure greater than $2P$.			
t'	80.9 cm.	—	—
$t' + 10$	84.9	—	0.0115
$t' + 15$	86.8	—	0.0115

Addition of a very small amount of mercuric iodide does not affect the first dissociation velocity K_1 and considerably increases the second dissociation velocity K_2 . With further addition of mercuric iodide the poisoning effect is easily noticeable.

TABLE XI.A.

Catalyst No. 3.

Wt. of $\text{HgI}_2 = 0.00848$ gm.

Wt. of catalyst = 8 gm. as Cu.

Temp. = 195° . $P = 29$ cm.

Time in mins.	Observed press.	K_1	K_2
t_1	35 cm.	—	—
$t_1 + 5$	39.4	0.039	—
$t_1 + 15$	46.0	0.0391	—
$t_1 + 30$	52.8	0.0414	—

For observed pressure greater than $2P$.

t	61 cm.	—
$t' + 15$	63.7	0.0069
$t' + 30$	66.3	0.00667

TABLE XIIB.

Wt. of $\text{HgI}_2 = 0.01246$ gm. $P = 27.8$ cm.

Time in mins.	Observed press.	K
t_1	30.5 cm.	—
$t_1 + 10$	33.8	0.0126

With increased addition of poison, the velocity constants K_1 and K_2 both continue to diminish until for an addition of 0.01246 gm. of mercuric iodide to 8 gm. of the copper catalyst, the poisoning is complete. It should be noted here, that since iodine has no depressing effect on the velocity constants the inhibiting action observed here is due to mercury atoms only.

Discussion.

Taylor (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1925, A 108, 105) suggests that the atoms on the surface of a catalytic material can exist in different degrees of valency saturation. Catalytic action will occur only on those "active" points of the surface where the extent of valency saturation is the least. The number of such active points per unit area of the catalyst surface will obviously depend on the method of preparation of the catalyst. Even if the chemical reaction on which the method of preparation is based remain the same, the number of active points developed per unit area may change considerably due to slight differences in the technique of manipulation. Thus in our experiments catalyst Nos. 1 and 2 had almost the same efficiency (velocity constants for dehydrogenation of pure methyl alcohol being 0.0267 and 0.0253 respectively), while catalyst No. 3 had a much higher efficiency (velocity constant for dehydrogenation being 0.0598). On the basis of Taylor's hypothesis, the number of active points per unit surface of catalyst No. 3 is 2.2 times that on surface of catalyst No. 1 or 2.

It has been observed before that chloroform and carbon disulphide in very small doses enhance the velocity of dehydrogenation of methyl alcohol at the beginning, but diminish very considerably from the beginning the velocity of decomposition of formaldehyde. The poisonous action of mercuric iodide is otherwise. In very small doses, it diminishes very considerably the velocity of dehydrogenation of methyl alcohol but the velocity of decomposition of formaldehyde is only slightly affected. It is clear therefore that these two reactions occur at different points of the catalyst surface, having different chemical and adsorptive properties. It is difficult to explain the accelerating effect of poisons like carbon disulphide and chloroform in very small doses on the velocity of dehydrogenation. It has a curious resemblance to the stimulating action of poisons in very small doses on living organisms.

A remarkable fact is easily noticed in the action of the poisons, carbon disulphide, chloroform and bromine in fairly large doses. *The diminution in the number of active points per unit area and hence the diminution in the velocity constants of dehydrogenation is proportional to the amount of poison added.* Thus we find, that for complete poisoning, 0.0329 gm. of carbon disulphide for 8 gm. of catalyst is required. In Table IV, we find that the velocity constant drops from 0.027 to 0.009 for an addition of 0.023 gm. of carbon disulphide.

We find $\frac{0.027-0.009}{0.027}$ or 0.66 is approximately equal to

$$\frac{0.023}{0.0329} \text{ or } 0.7.$$

Again in the case of chloroform, complete poisoning is effected by the addition of 0.0326 gm., while from Table VII we find that the velocity constant drops from 0.0253 to 0.0053 by an addition of 0.022 gm. of chloroform.

We find that $\frac{0.0253-0.0053}{0.025} = 0.8,$

$$\text{and } \frac{0.022}{0.0326} = 0.7 \text{ approximately.}$$

Considering the nature of experimental difficulties in determining the exact amount of poison necessary to inactivate completely the catalyst, the above values may be considered to be almost equal.

In the case of bromine, for complete poisoning 0.168 gm. is required, while to bring the velocity constant down from 0.06 to 0.02, 0.1 gm. of the poison is required (Table X).

$$\text{Here too, } \frac{0.06-0.02}{0.06} = 0.66, \text{ and } \frac{0.1}{0.168} = 0.6.$$

The ratios are approximately equal.

The experimental data on the amount of various poisons required to stop the reaction completely are given in Table XIV.

TABLE XIV.

Poisons.	Value of K_1 for each catalyst with pure methyl alcohol.	Total amount of poisonous substance required in gm.	Total amount of poisonous element required in gm. atoms of S, Cl, Br, and Hg.	Amount of poisonous element in gm. atom required for completely poisoning 1 gm. atom of the catalyst.	Amount of catalyst used in gm. atom.
1. CS_2	0.0267	0.0329	0.000864	0.00687	0.12568
2. CS_2	0.0267	0.0695	0.00182	0.00724	0.25136
3. CHCl_3	0.0253	0.0326	0.000819	0.00651	0.12568
4. Br_2	0.0598	0.01677	0.002009	0.01598	0.12566
5. HgI_2	0.0598	0.01246	0.0000274	0.000218	0.12568

It will be seen from horizontal columns (1) and (2) that with carbon disulphide as poison, as the quantity of catalyst is doubled, the quantity of the poison required for complete poisoning is doubled. From the horizontal columns (1), (2) and (3) it is evident that when a catalyst of the same efficiency is used, the ratio of the gram-atom of sulphur or chlorine to the gram-atom of the catalyst necessary for complete poisoning is approximately the same. Again from the horizontal column (4) we find that with bromine as poison, and with a catalyst whose efficiency is approximately $\frac{0.0598}{0.0267}$ or 2.2 times that of catalyst in column (1) or (2), the above ratio increases by about 2.2 times. We thus arrive at the remarkable conclusion that *an atom of bromine, an atom of sulphur (as CS₂) and an atom of chlorine (as CHCl₃) exhibit identical inhibiting power on the dehydrogenation of methyl alcohol by a copper catalyst.*

The behaviour of mercury as poison is fundamentally different. A very much smaller quantity of mercury is sufficient for complete poisoning. It is very probable that here the probable cause of inhibition is to be found in the destruction of the inhomogeneity of the catalytic copper surface due to mercury vapour. In the presence of mercury vapour, the copper surface with its active points where metal atoms are in a condition approximating to that of the gaseous phase, is quickly transformed into a perfect plane crystal face, by mercury vapour condensing on an active point, dissolving it and spreading it out in a smooth layer. The mercury now re-evaporates, condenses on another active point and this reaction is repeated in quick succession.

The experimental data, obtained with carbon tetrachloride or acetonitrile as poisons, do not lend themselves to serious theoretical considerations, as in these cases, the full effect of poison is not perceived immediately on the addition of the poison.

